

Extended Data

For 'Decline in diversity of tropical soil fauna under experimental warming'

Extended Data Figure 1. | One of five warmed plots at SWELTR. a, c the soil surface temperature shortly after the warming structure was switched on. **b, d** soil surface temperature after a period of thermal equilibration. The circular heating structure was 3.5 m in diameter and extended to 1.2 m depth, which resulted in an effective heated plot of approximately 5 m diameter by > 1.5 m depth (i.e. to the bedrock, situated at around 1.5–2.0 m across the study site). The experiment consisted of five warmed and control plot-pairs in total.

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11 **Extended Data Figure 2. | Soil fauna order level diversity, richness, and abundance with**
 12 **the exclusion of mites. a, c, e** Mean total diversity, taxonomic richness, and abundance,
 13 respectively, over the entire sampling period, from December 2019 to October 2020 for all taxa
 14 excluding oribatids and other acari. **b, d, f** Mean total diversity, richness, and abundance,
 15 respectively, by month. Box plots are standard Tukey plots, where the centre line represents the
 16 median, the lower and upper hinges represent the first and third quartiles, and whiskers represent
 17 + 1.5 the interquartile range. Blue lines and box plots in represent control plots while red lines

18 and box plots represent warmed plots. The shaded area in b represent the dry season (1 January
19 to 1 April) where precipitation was <50 mm per month. Warming treatment \times soil moisture
20 interaction and soil moisture were significant predictors of total invertebrate abundance in linear
21 mixed effects models, while only warming was a significant predictor for richness and diversity.
22 P values in **a**, **c**, and **e** are given for warming and moisture effects with significance denoted by
23 asterisks: $P < 0.05$ (*), $P < 0.01$ (**) and $P < 0.001$ (***)).

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25 **Extended Data Figure 3. | Litter faunal community composition and taxon-specific**26 **responses to three years of experimental soil warming.** Results are based on non-metric

27 multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination of soil invertebrate communities based on Bray-

28 Curtis dissimilarities. **a** The strength of the warming effect (250% to -250%) on the response of

29 specific taxa, where positive values indicate taxa were more abundant on warmed plots, and vice

30 versa. **b** NMDS spider diagram; $k = 2$; stress ≈ 0.1 . Each point on the spider diagram represents

31 the community composition for one plot on one sampling date, with warmed plots coloured red

32 and control plots coloured blue, circles representing the dry season, and triangles representing

33 the wet season. Relationships between taxa and treatments are represented by distance between

34 taxon names. Significant predictors are overlaid as vectors. The direction of each vector indicates

35 the direction of the gradient, while length indicates the strength of the correlation. Community

36 composition was significantly different between treatments ($P < 0.001$; PERMANOVA).

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39 **Extended Data Figure 4. | Effect of warming and drying on select soil taxa.** Mean abundance
 40 over the entire sampling period, from December 2019 to October 2020 for select soil taxa. Box
 41 plots are standard Tukey plots, where the centre line represents the median, the lower and upper

42 hinges represent the first and third quartiles, and whiskers represent + 1.5 the interquartile range,
43 and the point represents the mean with standard error bars. Blue lines represent control plots
44 while red lines represent warmed plots. Count values are per 1000 g dry soil, with effects plots
45 showing predicted count values for a given soil moisture. Plots for additional taxa are in
46 Supplementary Data. Significant P values for warming effect are denoted with asterisks for P <
47 0.05 (*), P < 0.01 (**), and P < 0.001 (***).

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50 **Extended Data Figure 5. | Soil temperature and moisture over time. a** Mean surface soil
51 temperature at time of sampling by month **b** Mean surface soil moisture at time of sampling by
52 month. Box plots are standard Tukey plots, where the centre line represents the median, the
53 lower and upper hinges represent the first and third quartiles, and whiskers represent + 1.5 the
54 interquartile range of the five plots of each treatment, each month. Blue box plots represent
55 control plots while red box plots represent warmed plots. The shaded areas represent the dry
56 season (1 January to 1 April) where precipitation was <50 mm per month. Surface temperature at
57 time of sampling was generally a little less than 4 °C higher on warmed plots. Wide range of soil
58 temperature values at the end of the experiment are the result of two warming plots losing power.
59 Surface soil moisture was generally slightly lower in warmed plots, and varied over the seasonal
60 cycle with a drop in the dry season followed by a gradual recovery to wet season moisture levels.
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63 **Extended Data Figure 6. | Precipitation on Barro Colorado Island Dec. 2019 – Oct. 2020.**

64 Data taken from Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute's Physical Monitoring Program[73,74]

65 on Barro Colorado Island (BCI). Annual average precipitation is 2657.8 mm, with a distinct dry

66 season in January-March. Samples were collected every month between December 2019 and

67 October 2020 except for April.

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70 **Extended Data Figure 7. | Mean seasonal leaf-litter moisture and standing crop. a and b**

71 Mean leaf-litter moisture in warmed and control plots during the wet and dry seasons,

72 respectively. c and d Mean leaf-litter standing crop (dry mass per area) in warmed and control

73 plots during the wet and dry seasons, respectively. Box plots are standard Tukey plots, where the

74 centre line represents the median, the lower and upper hinges represent the first and third

75 quartiles, and whiskers represent + 1.5 the interquartile range. Blue box plots represent control

76 plots while red box plots represent warmed plots. Moisture is higher in the wet season, and

77 standing crop is higher in the dry season, meanwhile treatment effects (warmed versus control)

78 are not significant (Treatment effect $P > 0.1$ for all panels; one-way ANOVA).

79 **Extended Data Table 1. Individual soil taxa.**

Taxon	Total count	Average count/1000 g dry soil (control)	Average count/1000 g dry soil (warm)	Percent difference	Warming P value	Moisture P value	Warming: moisture P value
Hymenoptera	3232	44.05	40.72	-8.16	0.14	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Coleoptera	602	10.11	5.49	-84.01	<0.001 ***	<0.01 **	<0.001 ***
Hemiptera	1538	12.45	25.90	51.92	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Diptera	85	2.40	0.81	-198.11	<0.001 ***	0.01 *	<0.001 ***
Blattodea	98	1.27	1.93	34.30	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.18
Thysanoptera	22	0.15	0.33	54.04	0.46	<0.001 ***	0.63
Psocoptera	12	0.17	0.11	-54.31	0.50	0.69	0.72
Lepidoptera	4	0.35	0.24	-43.17	0.97	<0.001 ***	0.07
Orthoptera	0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Trichoptera	0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Neuroptera	0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Zoraptera	0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Phthiraptora	2	0.05	0.00	-	-	-	-
Dermaptera	3	0.08	0.00	-	-	-	-
Protura	267	6.13	0.31	-1851.30	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.17
Diplura	290	6.00	2.33	-157.14	<0.001 ***	0.07	<0.01 **
Entomobryomorpha	2775	34.74	36.96	6.02	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Poduromorpha	114	2.44	0.69	-255.46	<0.001 ***	0.12	0.07
Symphyleona	985	14.08	10.63	-32.52	0.01 *	<0.001 ***	0.07
Oribatida	5269	41.82	94.67	55.82	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.02
Other Acari	8052	102.82	99.26	-3.59	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Araneae	119	0.54	2.29	76.34	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.12
Opiliones	5	0.05	0.07	25.09	0.69	0.73	0.59
Pseudoscorpiones	20	0.48	0.00	-	-	-	-
Ixodida	1	0.00	0.02	-	-	-	-
Schizomida	4	0.05	0.04	-20.57	0.97	0.26	0.18
Palpigradi	8	0.19	0.00	-	-	-	-
Chilopoda	26	0.56	0.06	-813.09	<0.001 ***	0.32	0.73
Diplopoda	203	3.34	2.31	-44.83	0.01 *	0.50	0.01 *
Symphyla	459	2.58	8.72	70.46	<0.001 ***	0.02 *	0.60
Tetramerocerata	229	4.72	1.52	-210.58	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.46
Isopoda	40	0.81	0.48	-71.27	0.29	<0.001 ***	0.02 *
Annelida	36	0.16	1.04	84.53	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.16
Gastropoda	0	-	-	-	-	-	-
Unknown	154	1.75	2.11	17.04	0.18	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***

80 Data are for the entire sampling period (14 December 2019 – 1 October 2020). P values were

81 produced for each taxon using an ANOVA run on a generalized linear effects model with a

82 Poisson distribution, and warming treatment, soil moisture, and the warming × soil moisture

83 interaction as fixed effects. Significant P values are in bold and highlighted by asterisks for P <
84 0.05 (*), P < 0.01 (**) and P < 0.001 (***)).

85 **Extended Data Table 2. Individual litter taxa.**

Taxon	Total count	Average count/1000 g fresh litter (control)	Average count/1000 g fresh litter (warm)	Percent difference	Warming P value	Moisture P value	Warming:moisture P value
Hymenoptera	2571	371.66	110.02	-237.79	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Coleoptera	505	54.65	35.92	-52.14	<0.001 ***	<0.01 **	<0.001 ***
Hemiptera	200	22.56	15.27	-47.73	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.75
Diptera	308	25.12	33.88	25.84	0.73	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Blattodea	231	8.91	37.15	76.03	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Thysanoptera	316	28.05	35.25	20.43	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Psocoptera	155	19.07	11.99	-59.09	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Lepidoptera	33	3.57	2.74	-29.95	<0.01 **	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Orthoptera	6	0.58	0.38	-53.00	0.19	0.46	<0.001 ***
Trichoptera	3	0.00	0.73	-	-	-	-
Neuroptera	2	0.26	0.20	-33.67	-	-	-
Zoraptera	1	0.25	0.00	-	-	-	-
Phthiraptora	0	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-
Dermaptera	0	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-
Protura	11	2.83	0.00	-	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	1.00
Diplura	25	2.67	1.37	-93.95	0.02 *	<0.01 **	<0.001 ***
Entomobryomorpha	3194	306.32	278.31	-10.06	0.01 *	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Poduromorpha	428	38.03	45.11	15.69	0.96	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Symphyleona	1484	121.00	95.68	-26.47	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Oribatida	14972	1099.39	1703.02	35.44	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Other Acari	23745	2201.62	2571.55	14.39	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Araneae	121	11.28	11.04	-2.20	0.01 *	<0.001 ***	<0.01 **
Opiliones	47	4.86	3.62	-34.02	<0.01 **	0.22	<0.001 ***
Pseudoscorpiones	71	11.28	2.94	-283.81	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.05
Ixodida	3	0.51	0.08	-535.54	<0.001 ***	0.03 *	<0.01 **
Schizomida	1	0.00	0.08	-	-	-	-
Palpigradi	0	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-
Chilopoda	8	1.30	0.37	-252.00	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.23
Diplopoda	70	8.93	3.88	-130.45	<0.001 ***	0.01 *	<0.001 ***
Symphyla	82	2.16	12.64	82.88	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.57
Tetramerocerata	68	13.22	1.57	-742.07	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Isopoda	60	10.92	0.98	-1015.45	<0.001 ***	0.07	<0.01 **
Annelida	4	0.44	0.37	-17.83	0.96	0.21	0.78
Gastropoda	6	1.00	0.57	-76.17	<0.01 **	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***
Unknown	126	16.12	10.39	-55.12	<0.001 ***	<0.001 ***	0.05

86 Data are for three months (14 December 2019 – 14 February 2020). P values were produced for
87 each taxon using an ANOVA run on a generalized linear effects model with a Poisson
88 distribution, and warming treatment, soil-under-litter moisture, and the warming × soil-under-
89 litter moisture interaction as fixed effects. Significant P values are in bold and highlighted by
90 asterisks for P < 0.05 (*), P < 0.01 (**) and P < 0.001 (***).

91 **Extended Data Table 3. Average monthly diversity indexes for soil fauna.**

Date	Treatment	Total abundance (count/1000 g dry soil)	Taxonomic richness	Shannon Index	Pielou's evenness	Simpson Index
2019-12-14	W	188.74	7.6	1.65	0.82	0.73
	C	256.99	8.6	1.74	0.83	0.77
2020-01-16	W	246.70	11.0	1.68	0.70	0.75
	C	170.15	13.2	2.01	0.78	0.81
2020-02-14	W	284.76	13.8	1.73	0.66	0.75
	C	341.38	13.8	1.89	0.72	0.78
2020-03-16	W	435.75	13.8	1.45	0.56	0.67
	C	285.34	14.2	1.72	0.65	0.72
2020-05-01	W	703.82	12.2	1.42	0.58	0.66
	C	729.65	15.2	1.45	0.54	0.62
2020-06-01	W	322.26	12.2	1.81	0.73	0.79
	C	292.23	16.0	1.99	0.72	0.81
2020-07-01	W	358.88	12.7	1.83	0.72	0.78
	C	204.87	12.7	1.92	0.75	0.80
2020-08-03	W	339.28	14.3	1.86	0.70	0.78
	C	229.44	15.3	2.01	0.75	0.81
2020-09-02	W	286.15	11.8	1.83	0.74	0.78
	C	239.52	13.6	2.00	0.77	0.83
2020-10-01	W	232.00	12.6	1.97	0.78	0.82
	C	145.07	13.6	2.06	0.79	0.83

92 Each value represents the mean value for the plots of the same treatment type in the same month.

93 Average abundance is greater in warmed plots for most months, while average order level

94 taxonomic richness, diversity, and evenness are greater in control plots. Values for

95 diversity/evenness indexes were calculated using the ‘Vegan’ package [78] in R version 4.1.1[79].

96 Shannon diversity was used for statistical models (other diversity indices showed the same

97 trends).